

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF GENDER ON PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING DURING ADOLESCENCE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was investigated to Psychological well-being in Adolescence of Gender Difference. The random sampling method was used in this study. The total sample consisted 60 Adolescent. 30 of Girls and 30 of Boys of 11th standard students selected from Bhavnagar City. The research tool for Psychological Well-being Scale developed by Sudha Bhogle (1995). In this research psychological well-being Inventory was used for data collection. Data was analyzed by 't' test verify the hypothesis. The result shows that 't' value is 3.34. that is significant at 0.01 level. So, the hypothesis is not accepted. It means Girls and Boys was very far difference between psychological well-being in adolescent period.

Key words: Psychological Well-being

1. INTRODUCTION

Psychological well-being is a state of mind desirable for one and all. Some of the characteristics associated with psychological well-being are: Optimism, positive work attitudes, understanding, reaching out of people, maintaining good health, ability to sustain relationships, able to handle crisis effectively etc. The above characteristics sound utopian in the context of present day life style. Society today is driven by competition and is putting pressure on the people.

Well-being is a concept that encompasses a Well-rounded, balanced, and comprehensive experience of life. It includes health in social, physical, mental emotional, career and spiritual domains.

Well-being is when we are at a place in life where everything was come together and were round and comfortable with what has, is, and will take place. Understanding and incorporating the above ideas can bring greater wisdom self awareness and psychological well-being.

Positive psychological definition of well-being generally includes some of six general characteristics. The six characteristics of well-being most prevalent in definitions of well-being are:

- The active pursuit of well-being;
- A balance of attributes;
- Positive affect or life satisfaction;
- Provincial behavior;
- Multiple dimensions; and
- Personal optimization.

Adolescence is a transitional stage of physical and human development that generally occurs during the period from puberty to legal adulthood. The period of adolescence is most closely associated with the teenage years, though its physical, psychological and cultural expressions may begin earlier and end later.

The teenage years are also called adolescence. During this time, parents will see the greatest amount of growth in height and weight in their child. Adolescence is a firm for growth sports and puberty changes. An adolescent may grow several inches in several months followed by a period of very slow growth, and then have another growth spurt. Changes with puberty may occur gradually or several signs may become visible at the same time.

There is a great amount of variation in the rate of changes that may occur. Some teenagers may experience these signs of maturity sooner or later others. The following indicates the average for adolescents 13 to 18 years old.

As we venture into the dawn of the new millennium adolescent development has emerged as a major area of psychological research. Adolescents have long been regarded as a group of people who are searching for themselves to find some from of identity and meaning in their lives. They have also been regarded as a unique group with a wide range of difficulties and problems in their transition to adulthood.

One aspect of adolescents is their emotions, and within schools and society as a whole, this aspect has often been overlooked. Students are measured in terms of their performance and grades.

Adolescence stage is a period of transition in which a person is faced with challenges and difficulties that may throw him in to confusion and troubles. However, it is also a period where young men and women could be prepared for adult life ahead. Understanding the well - being of adolescents and the factor that contribute to it will help towards clarifying and defining ways to better help adolescents prepare for adult life. One of the questions that has gained interest in the study among adolescents is whether there is difference in psychological well- being between males and females (Roothman, Kirsten & Wissing, 2003)

Investigating gender differences in psychological well - being is important as not all people are identical. Considering differences among them will help in the effort to empower individuals to achieve their full - potential and self actualization. Recent studies on gender differences in psychological well - being have yielded contradictory findings which underscores the need to study more on the impact of gender on important well - being outcomes.

The moderating roles of age and gender on psychological well- being have been reported in the literature. but neither have been widely examined nor examined at all in the contest of testing the latent and main fest benefits' hypotheses.

What take place during adolescence is much intertwined with that has come before and what will follow. As adolescences is the time of rapid physical and accompanying psychological changes, the earlier developed sameness and continuities are questioned again. The growing and developing young people. Faced with the psychological revolution within them are more conceded now with attempts at consolidating their social roles.

Psychological well- being is viewed in different ways. One views if according to the hedonic and eudemonic approaches of early philosopher s. subjective well - being was coined by Ryan and Deci (2001) as composed of perception of pleasure, displeasure, satisfaction and happiness which runs along the hedonic approach. Another way is the eudemonic approach or

the psychological well-being model that takes into account the mechanisms of health functioning and adjustment. Psychological well-being (PWB) is said to be more stable than subjective well-being which could fluctuate with life experiences. It is also argued that PWB could lead to adaptive human functioning and positive life experiences. Other recent proposal take on the existential approach of psychological well-being that argues that the good life is not being free of pain and difficulties but one that is lived in spite of it not being free of pain and difficulties but on that is lived in spite of it.

2. RELATED STUDY

- Jeamioe A Perel "Gender Difference in Psychological well-being among Filipino College Student Samples" Dela Salle University- Dasmarians, Cavite, Philippines.
- Pater A Creed & Tania Watson, "Age, gender, Psychological Well-being and the impact of losing the latent and manifest benefits of employment in unemployed people" Griffith University.

3. OBJECTIVE

- To compare the study of Psychological well-being among Girls and Boys Adolescent.

4. HYPOTHESIS

There is no significant difference on psychological well-being among Girls and Boys adolescent.

5. VARIABLE

(i) Independent Variable

- A. 11th Standard Students at two levels
- A₁ Girls Adolescent
- A₂ Boys Adolescent

(ii) Depended Variable:-

- To get score on Psychological well-being among Girls and Boys Adolescent.

6. SAMPLE

The sample consisted of 60 Adolescent. (30 of Girls and 30 of Boys of 11th Standard) the sample was selected by random method from BHANAVNAGAR City.

7. TOOLS

In this research Psychological Well-being. Questionnaire where used from the data collection. It was constructed and standardized by Sudha Bhogle (1995). They have made English version scale but investigator has used Gujarati Version Scale made by Pankaj Suvera (2000) the reliability is 0.85 and the validity was very high.

8. RESEARCH DESIGN

- A. 11th Standard Students at two levels
- A₁ Girls Adolescent
- A₂ Boys Adolescent

9. STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

Hear in this study "t" test was used for date interpretation.

RESULT TABLE

Variable	Sample (N)	Mean	S.D.	SED	't' value	level of significance
Girls	30	21.50	3.02	0.89	3.34	0.01
Boys	30	18.53	3.93			

Significance = 0.01 = 2.66

10. RESULT DICISTION

The main objective of present study was a study of Psychological Well- being among Girls and Boys Adolescent. In it statistical 't' method was used. A result discussion of present study is as under.

The result obtained on the Psychological Well- being reveals significant difference of Girls and Boys Adolescent.

The Girls students received higher mean score 21.50 as compared to the Boy students. There has mean difference was 18.53 and the standard deviation score of Girl Students received 3.02 and the Boy students received 3.93. So we can say that Girl students have a good Psychological Well- being than Boy students. the 't' value of Psychological Well- being was 3.34.

According to the 't' test the numeric value that we get is 3.34 which is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore the hypothesis that there is no significant difference on psychological well-being among Girls and Boys Adolescent is not acceptable. It means there is significant difference in Psychological Well- being among Girls and Boys Adolescent.

So, this study examined Psychological well-being in adolescence of Gender differences in the effects of menarche in females and voice change in males. Specifically with regard to depression, self- esteem, body image, and externalizing problems, participants were 60 Youths aged 16 to 17.

11. CONCLUSION

There is significant difference in Psychological Well-being between Girls and Boys Adolescent. ($t= 3.34$)

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